

A novel test method to induce bi-axial stress states in thin-ply composites under combined longitudinal compression and transverse tension

Tamas Rev

F.-X. Irisarri, P. Paulmier, F. Laurin and M. R. Wisnom

Melbourne, 15th of August, 2019

bristol.ac.uk/composites

EPSRC

Engineering and Physical Sciences
Research Council

EPSRC Centre for Doctoral Training
in Advanced Composites
for Innovation and Science

22nd International Conference
on Composite Materials
11-16th August,
Melbourne,
Australia

**ALUMNI
AND FRIENDS**

ONERA

Introduction and design

- **Objectives:**
 - Determine compressive strain
 - With no grip effects and in-plane damage prior final failure
 - Assess the effect of transverse tension on compression failure
- **Design**
 - Novel tensile test method to determine ***longitudinal compressive*** strength
 - ***Thin-ply*** carbon/epoxy material (TC33/K51) → suppressing undesired damage

Lay-up design

- Optimizing lay-up
 - To enable fibre compressive failure and
 - To maximize transverse tensile stresses
- Tools for optimization
 - Advanced failure and damage model – ONERA Progressive Failure Model (OPFM) [2]
 - Design of Experiments (DOE) defined by lamination parameters (V_1 , V_3)
- Identification of OPFM model on TC33/K51 material (Longitudinal/Transverse tension, Shear)
- Chosen configuration:
 $[(\pm 45)_6/90_2]_s$

All possible laminates and their *first ply failure (FPF)* mode

Damage analysis

• In-situ

Gauge section compressive failure: kink bands!

• Post-mortem

No delamination/cracks detected!

Control with C-Scan 98% of failure load

• Interrupted

Identification of longitudinal compressive strength/strain

- Longitudinal compressive strain is directly measured
 $\epsilon_{yy} = \epsilon_{11}$ in 90° plies
 - $X\epsilon_c = -1.21\%$ (C.o.V - 2.15%)
- Inverse identification of longitudinal compressive strength
 - $X_c = -964\text{MPa}$ (C.o.V - 2.1%)
- Slightly non-linear behaviour well captured by OPFM

Conclusions

- Novel test method to determine longitudinal compressive strength under a biaxial stress state
- Fibre compressive gauge section failure observed in 90° plies!
- Thin-ply materials successfully utilized to suppress undesired damage prior failure
- OPFM prediction successfully validated by experimental data

Thank you for listening!
Any questions?
tamas.rev@bristol.ac.uk

References

- [1] Laurin F., Paulmier P., and Irisarri F.-X. , “Determination of the longitudinal compressive strength of a CFRP ply through a tensile test on a laminate,” Compos. Part A Appl. Sci.Manuf., vol. 113, pp. 209–219, Oct. 2018.
- [2] Laurin F, Carrère N, Maire JF. A multiscale progressive failure approach for composite laminates based on thermodynamical viscoelastic and damage models. Compos Part A Appl Sci Manuf 2007;38:198–209